

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Mobile Technology's Role in Meeting Sustainable Development Goals

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Abstract

It has become increasingly important for companies in the twenty-first century to consider environmental sustainability. Various industries have taken varied approaches to environmental protection. Every major cell phone company has gotten behind this great cause at some point. The digital divide exists even in the most remote regions of the world, where there is little or no infrastructure. Cellular technology adoption continues to climb even as prices come down for smart phones and the availability of reliable networks expands. Because mobile devices are so widely available and frequently used, many forward-thinking individuals are turning to them to help eliminate knowledge gaps, alleviate poverty, and enhance the environment. According to the GSMA's sixth annual SDG impact report, the mobile industry's contribution to all 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) increased in 2020. We are barely half-way to our potential impact on attaining the Sustainable Development Goals because of this worldwide pandemic. Given that the 2030 SDG targets are only 10 years away, progress cannot be taken for granted. There is a strong correlation between mobile phone uses in all the countries of the world. Thus, the purpose of the study is to demonstrate how mobile technology helps achieve long-term sustainable development goals.

Keywords: Mobile Technology; SDGs; Poverty and Contribution etc

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1.Introduction

The mobile sector contributes to a sustainable, robust, and high-quality infrastructure. They are dedicated to using the internet and digital solutions to advance the 2030 Agenda and speed up the SDGs (SDGs). They can make a significant contribution to a global effort that will leave no one behind. According to GSMA, an organization that brings together the world's main mobile operators, connectivity is crucial for meeting the UN's 17 Sustainable Development Goals. In February 2016, at the Mobile World Congress (MWC) in Barcelona, Spain, the mobile sector committed to working toward the UN's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Since then, MWC's contributions to the SDGs have been gathered into the 2017 "Mobile Industry Impact Report." The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) were launched in September 2015 as a 17-point plan to achieve equitable and long-term health on all scales, from the planet's biosphere to individual communities (GSMA, 2021). The goal is to alleviate poverty, maintain the environment, and ensure future peace and prosperity. 300 telecoms companies from around the world detail their contributions to the 2030

targets.(GSMA, 2020 Mobile Industry SDG Impact Report, 2020)

The article's findings are based on analyses of mobile industry-sponsored activities. These include using communication to help local companies and creating jobs for the poor. Each Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) is given a score from 0 to 100 based on its importance. An SDG score of 37.5 means the industry is providing 37.5% of what it can to achieving this SDG. The mobile phone sector has been at the forefront of inventing innovative products and surviving in the current climate. These include techniques to(GSMA, 2021) survive in the existing environment. The mobile phone business has produced smaller, lighter phones to lessen their environmental impact (Technology & Environmental Sustainability Initiatives). (GSMA, 2020 Mobile Industry SDG Impact Report, 2020).

Smaller gadgets require less energy during travel, recycling, and reuse, and less raw material and shipping space. Mobile phone manuals are only available digitally. This reduces tree-made paper use. The mobile phone industry uses innovation to establish an eco-friendly ecosystem. Solar-